

PRINCIPLES OF APPLICATION AND REQUIREMENTS FOR THE SELECTION OF MULTIMEDIA MATERIALS FOR TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The transition to a market path of economic development in our country led to the formulation and solution of a number of priority tasks. Among them, an important place is occupied by a set of issues related to the systematic introduction of information and communication technologies in the field of education, which today offer new perspectives and amazing opportunities for learning, thereby confirming that humanity is on the verge of an educational revolution. The purpose of writing the article is to analyze the Blackboard distance learning system based on a wide institutional application in educational institutions of foreign countries and the possibility of its effective application in Uzbekistan.

The fundamental changes in all areas of human life that these information and communication technologies and new models of activity bring with them, coupled with the new social requirements of the world community, require a completely different level of literacy that meets the needs of the information society.

There is an acute problem of creating a fundamentally new technology for acquiring scientific knowledge, new pedagogical approaches to teaching and mastering knowledge, new courses of study and teaching methods. All this should contribute to the activation of the intellect of the trainees, the formation of their creative and mental abilities, the development of a holistic worldview of the individual - a full member of the information society [1].

Conducting education on the basis of new pedagogical technologies determines efficiency and achievement of goals. It is clear that the closer the result is to the goal, the more effective the educational process, and this is one of the important aspects of the implementation of modern technical means of education and advanced technologies [5].

Innovations are characteristic of any professional human activity and therefore naturally become the subject of study, analysis and implementation. Innovations do not arise by themselves, they are the result of scientific research, advanced pedagogical experience of individual teachers and entire teams. This process cannot be spontaneous, it needs to be managed.

In the context of an innovative strategy for a holistic pedagogical process in vocational education, the role of the rector of the university, deans and teachers as direct carriers of innovative processes is significantly increasing. With all the variety of teaching technologies: didactic, computer, problematic, modular and others, the implementation of the leading pedagogical processes remains with the teachers. With the introduction of modern technologies into the educational process, the teacher increasingly acts not as a distributor of information (as is traditionally accepted), but as a consultant, adviser, sometimes even a colleague of the student. This gives some positive aspects: students actively participate in the learning process, learn to think independently, put forward their points of view, simulate real situations.

The new educational multimedia environment creates additional opportunities for the development of students' creativity, stimulates their curiosity, instills interest in scientific activities.

Thus, multimedia is an extremely useful and fruitful educational technology due to its inherent qualities of interactivity, flexibility, and integration of various types of multimedia educational information, as well as due to the ability to take into account the individual characteristics of students and help increase their motivation.

With regard to the pedagogical process in vocational education, innovation means the introduction of something new in the goals, content, methods and forms of education, the organization of joint activities of teachers and students.

One of the types of innovations in the organization of education at the present stage is the introduction of distance learning. It seems necessary to consider this type of training as an accompaniment of the educational process.

The modern period of development of a civilized society is characterized by the process of informatization. This is a global social process in which the collection, accumulation, processing, storage, transmission and use of information is carried out on the basis of modern means of communication.

The introduction of modern information technology tools into the education system makes it possible to improve the mechanisms for managing the education system based on the use of communication networks, improve methods, forms and content in accordance with the tasks of developing the personality of a student in modern conditions of informatization of society. This helps to form the ability to independently acquire knowledge and conduct research activities, use computer systems for diagnostics, testing and control of knowledge [3].

Currently, teaching Russian language in higher education is undergoing great changes. New information technologies, such as the Internet, audio and video complexes, multimedia educational computer programs, began to be introduced into the educational process more intensively.

Multimedia technologies are a combination of different ways of learning: texts, graphics, music, videos and animations in an interactive mode. The new learning environment creates additional opportunities for the development of students' creativity, stimulates their curiosity, instills interest in scientific activity [2]. Modern multimedia programs are an effective means of optimizing the conditions of mental work. Forms of work with computer training programs

in Russian language classes include learning vocabulary, practicing pronunciation, learning monologue and dialogic speech, learning writing, learning grammar.

In Russian language class, you can solve a number of didactic tasks using Internet materials, replenish students' vocabulary and develop reading skills and abilities; improve writing skills; create sustainable motivation for learning Russian language. For students, multimedia technologies are a way by which they expand their understanding of the world around them.

The use of multimedia technologies provides more complete and accurate information about the phenomena and objects under study. This improves the quality of learning, allows you to satisfy and develop the cognitive interests of students, increases the visibility of learning, allowing you to use hard-to-reach material or one that cannot be used without a computer [1].

The work of students becomes more intense, which allows you to increase the pace of studying educational material and increase the amount of independent work in the classroom and after them.

As practice shows, multimedia programs best fit the structure of the educational process. They bring the process of teaching Russian language as close as possible to real conditions, most fully meet didactic requirements. These programs use methodological techniques that allow for familiarization, training and control [5].

The effective use of multimedia technologies in the educational process is possible only if the relevant technologies are harmoniously and reasonably integrated into this process and provide new opportunities for both the teacher and the students. For the effective use of multimedia technologies, it is necessary to create such conditions to ensure the formation of social and cognitive activity as the main personal characteristics of the student. Programs should be interactive in order to develop the independence of trainees. In order to further self-realization of students, it is necessary to develop their abilities and harmonious personality.

Technical means in Russian language class should increase interest in language learning and labor productivity, provide feedback and control all the actions of students [4].

It should be noted that the use of multimedia technologies cannot provide a significant pedagogical effect without a teacher, since these technologies are only teaching methods, the effectiveness of which depends on the ability of the teacher to use them to achieve certain pedagogical goals based on a deep study of all possibilities. Not surprisingly, not all teachers were ready for the widespread introduction of computers in teaching Russian language. It is necessary that every teacher understand a simple idea: a computer in the educational process is not a mechanical teacher, not a substitute or analogue of a teacher, but a tool that enhances and expands the possibilities of his teaching activity [2].

The upbringing of a creative personality is the task of the entire education system, since in the process of cognitive creative activity, the student realizes his importance, realizes himself as a person. For the formation of creativity as a personal quality, it is necessary to create a specially organized environment that will provide a multilateral systemic influence. Students should be given the opportunity to work individually. For this, it is logical to introduce elements of distance learning based on the use of multimedia technologies [5].

Modernity makes ever higher demands on teaching the practical knowledge of a Russian language in everyday communication and in the professional sphere. The volume of information is growing, and often the routine methods of its transmission, storage and processing are inefficient. The use of information technology reveals the enormous potential of the computer as a means of learning. Multimedia learning programs have huge advantages over traditional teaching methods. They allow you to train various types of speech activity and combine them in various combinations; help to create communicative situations, automate language and speech actions; contribute to the implementation of an individual approach and the intensification of the student's independent work.

Thus, the educational potential of multimedia tools contributes to the development of a deep approach to learning [2]. However, in itself does not contribute to the understanding of the information by the trainees.

In other words, various types of concepts of learning with the use of multimedia arise, which are divided into quantitative and qualitative [4]. This means that the concepts of learning with multimedia are derived from the general concepts of learning.

Some of them consider multimedia as a way of acquiring a large amount of knowledge, which can be considered as a quantitative approach to learning (i.e. collecting information); while the means to achieve this goal is the computer.

In this way, multimedia can help learners develop a deeper approach to learning than what they consider appropriate for themselves. Multimedia is presented as a means of enhancing the effectiveness of learning (for example, by increasing motivation), perhaps in part due to the fact that they involve the learner more in the learning process. However, students can consider multimedia only as a means of accelerating the learning process and reducing the "information load", i.e. as a means of surface learning.

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